

Synthesis and anticancer activity evaluation of substituted carbazole bearing thiosemicarbazide derivatives against human glioma U87 MG cell line

Nitin Kumar *, Vishal Nemaish and Pratibha Mehta Luthra

Neuro-pharmaceutical Research Laboratory, Dr. BR. Ambedkar Centre for Biomedical Research (ACBR), University of Delhi, 110007, India.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 16(03), 884–892

Publication history: Received on 11 November 2022; revised on 21 December 2022; accepted on 24 December 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.16.3.1402>

Abstract

Both carbazole and thiosemicarbazide scaffold showed various potential biological activities in medicinal chemistry. In this research work, we synthesized a series of carbazole bearing thiosemicarbazide derivatives (17-28) and evaluated their *in vitro* cytotoxicity (IC₅₀) profile on the U87 MG cell line using MTT assay. All target compounds were well characterized by NMR and HRMS mass spectroscopy. In series, six compounds (17, 20, 21, 22, 23, 28) found better *in vitro* cytotoxicity (IC₅₀) values were 26.50 μM, 34.0 μM, 39 μM, 80 μM, 62 μM, 50 μM respectively compare to standard drug Temozolomide (IC₅₀ = 100 μM). The SAR study of all final compounds (17-28) were also analyzed on the basis of different substituents on 6th position of carbazole scaffold bearing thiosemicarbazide derivatives against U87 MG cell line. All of the above studies showed that carbazole bearing thiosemicarbazide derivatives (17-28) showed anticipated anticancer activity against U87 MG glioma cell line.

Keywords: GBM (Glioblastoma); Carbazole; Thiosemicarbazide; TMZ (Temozolomide); Compound 17((E)-2-((1,4-dimethyl-9-H-carbazol-3-yl)methylene)hydrazinecarbothioamide); SAR (Structure activity relationship); MTT (tetrazolium salt (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide)

1 Introduction

Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) is a type IV grade tumor according to WHO grading and classification [1,2]. GBM is a most deadly, aggressive and undifferentiated type of tumor originated from glial cell in the brain. The current treatment standard is a multimodal approach combining neurosurgery, fractionated radiation therapy, and chemotherapy [3, 4]. However, GBM patients usually have a median survival of approximately 14 to 15 months from the diagnosis [3]. Temozolomide (TMZ), is the only anticancer drug has been reported to improve the survival in a phase III study of GBM when administered concomitant with the radiotherapy [5].

Carbazole derivatives showed potential biological and photophysical properties [6-11]. Carbazole derivatives can target DNA structures and has prospective for development into anticancer drugs [6, 9]. Carbazole, a tricyclic planar structure, makes it prone to interact with DNA either via intercalation or minor groove binding well established in literature [9-11]. 1,4-Dimethyl-9-H-carbazole structure part is present in Ellipticine (5,11-dimethyl-6-H-pyrido[4,3-b]carbazole), acts as an intercalative agent and blocks topoisomerase II activity only [6, 9, 12] Anna Caruso et al. designed and synthesized 3,6 substituted carbazole linked to guanidine derivatives (1) showed potential *in vitro* cytotoxicity (IC₅₀) value 3.1 μM against HL-60 cell line [12]. Earlier our group reported substituted bis carbazole derivatives (2) showed potential *in vitro* cytotoxicity (IC₅₀) against human glioma U87 MG cell line [9]. G.A. Ciftci et al. reported apoptotic effect of compound 2-[(9-ethyl-9H-carbazol-3-yl)amino]-2-oxoethyl N,N-disubstituted dithiocarbamates (3) showed good *in*

* Corresponding author: Nitin Kumar

Neuro-pharmaceutical Research Laboratory, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar Centre For Biomedical Research (ACBR), University of Delhi, Delhi, 110007, India.

in vitro cytotoxicity value (IC_{50}) 3.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ on C6 (glioma) cell line [13]. Bis(carbazole-2,9N-benzyl)-3-ethyl ethanoate (BC3EE2, 9B) **4** showed potential significant *in vitro* antitumor activities on the two glioma GBM8401 ($IC_{50} = 5 \mu\text{M}$) and GBM8901 ($IC_{50} = 7 \mu\text{M}$) cell lines [14]. Philippe Diaz and co-workers reported modified carbazoles derivatives (**5**) showed potential *in vitro* anticancer activity ($IC_{50} = 80 \text{ nM}$) against glioma cell line [15] (Figure.1)

Figure 1 Structure of some carbazole scaffold based anticancer potential molecules against glioma cell line (1-5)

During the last decades, thiosemicarbazones structure based compounds have been clinically developed for a variety of diseases including tuberculosis, viral infections, malaria and cancer [16, 17]. Thiosemicarbazones have a thiourea moiety contain conjugated N–N–S tridentate ligand system ($\text{NH}_2\text{–CS–NH–NH}_2$), which is crucial role for anticancer activity [18]. In 1956 Brockman et al. reported anti-leukemic effect of 2-formylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (PT) **6** but this compound was found to be cumulatively toxic [19]. In 1963 French and col. formulated hypotheses about the mode of action of the $\alpha(\text{N})$ -heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones (**7**). The first was that they were acting as tridentate ligands and the second was that modifying the ring system while retaining the ligand pattern could lead to improved activity and decreased toxicity. The electron densities, substituent's and geometry could have critical effects on activity [20] Triapine (**8**) has potential anticancer activity and is undergoing phase-2 clinical trial for the treatment of solid tumors such as cervical and vaginal cancer [21, 22] (Figure 2). COTI-2 (**9**) entered a clinical phase I trial for treatment of advanced or recurrent gynecologic malignancies. DpC(di-2-pyridylketone-4-cyclohexyl-4-methyl-3-thiosemicarbazone) **10** also entered in clinical phase I evaluation since January 2016 [21, 22] (Figure. 2).

Figure 2 Structure of potent anticancer thiosemicarbazides based derivatives (6-10)

Schiff bases containing azomethine ($-C=N-$) or imine functional group and are established to be a versatile pharmacophore for design and development of various bioactive lead compounds [23-24].

Considering the important biological activities of carbazole and thiosemicarbazide derivatives, herein we report design, synthesis and *in vitro* anticancer activity of substituted carbazole bearing thiosemicarbazides derivatives. All final compounds (**17-28**) were evaluated for *in vitro* anticancer activity (IC_{50}) against the U87 MG cell line using the MTT assay for 24 time period.

2 Material and methods

All organic and biological chemicals were purchased from Spectrochem Private ltd. India, Sigma-Aldrich Co. USA, Hi-Media, Alpha Aesar and used without further purification.

2.1 MTT Assay

Treatment of cells (5×10^3 U87MG) with various concentrations ($1 \mu M$ to $250 \mu M$) of compound (**17-28**) for 24 h time period. The IC_{50} value was calculated using the MTT assay reported formula in previous papers [9, 25]. All experiments were performed in triplicate, and the relative cell viability (%) was expressed as a percentage relative to the untreated control cells.

2.2 Synthesis of compound (17-28)

Starting material 6-substituted 1,4-dimethyl-9-H-carbazol-3-carbaldehyde ($R=H, F, Cl, Br, OCH_3, OH$) (**11-16**) intermediate reported in our and other research groups previous method [9, 26, 27]. Equimolar amount of 6-substituted 1,4-dimethyl-9-H-carbazol-3-carbaldehyde (**11-16**) intermediate and substituted thiosemicarbazides ($R=H, CH_3$) were dissolved in ethanol reflux for 4-6 h (SCHEME 1) (Figure 3) [28]. Progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC using petroleum

ether: ethyl acetate (7:3) or chloroform: methanol (9:1) system. After completion of the reaction, the solid product that appeared out on cooling overnight was filtered, washed twice with ethanol: water (2:8), dried it and used without any further purification.

Figure 3 Reagent & condition (C) Substituted thiosemicarbazides, Ethanol, reflux, 4-6 h (**Scheme 1**)

- (E)-2-((1,4-dimethyl-9-*H*-carbazol-3-yl)methylene)hydrazinecarbothioamide (**17**). Yield: 80 %; off white solid; mp: 224°C; ¹H NMR(400MHz-dmso-d₆): δ(ppm) 11.35(1-NH-N, br-s), 11.25(1-NH-indole, br-s), 8.69(CH=N, s), 8.01(H, s, aromatic), 7.90 & 8.123 (2H, NH₂, br-s), 7.45 (d, 1H, aromatic), 7.522(m, 2-H, aromatic), 2.77(3H, s, CH₃), 2.56(3H, s, CH₃), HRMS(ESI-Q-TOF): C₁₆H₁₆N₄S [M + H]⁺ calcd *m/z*, 296.1095, found *m/z*(M+1) 297.1165
- (E)-2-((6-fluoro-1,4-dimethyl-9-*H*-carbazol-3-yl)methylene)hydrazinecarbo thioamide (**18**). Yield: 70%. Off white solid; mp: 285°C. ¹H NMR(400 MHz-dmso-d₆): δ(ppm); 11.35(1-NH, br-s), 11.00(1-NH-N, br-s), 8.5(CH=N, s), 8.10 and 7.90 (2H, NH₂ br, s), 8.18(1-H, d, aromatic), 7.89(1H, s, aromatic), 7.51(d, 1-H, aromatic), 7.40(d, 1H, aromatic), 7.15(1-H, aromatic), 2.77(3H, s, CH₃), 2.56(3-H, s, CH₃), HRMS(ESI-Q-TOF): C₁₆H₁₅FN₄S [M+H]⁺ calcd *m/z*, 314.1001, found *m/z*(M+1) 315.1256.
- (E)-2-((6-chloro-1,4-dimethyl-9-*H*-carbazol-3-yl)methylene)hydrazinecarbothioamide (**19**). Yield :70%. Off white solid; mp: 235°C. ¹H NMR(400 MHz-dmso-d₆): δ(ppm) 11.70(1-NH, br-s), 11.35(1-NH-N, br-s), 8.5(CH=N, s), 8.18(1-H, d, aromatic), 8.23 & 7.90 (2H, -NH₂, brs), 7.89(1-H, s, aromatic), 7.51(d, 1-H, aromatic), 7.40(d, 1-H), 7.15(1-H, Aromatic), 2.77(3-H, s), 2.56(3-H, s). HRMS (ESI-Q-TOF): C₁₆H₁₅ClN₄S [M + H]⁺ calcd *m/z* 330.0705 found *m/z*(M+1) 331.0806
- (E)-2-((6-bromo-1,4-dimethyl-9-*H*-carbazol-3-yl)methylene)hydrazinecarbothioamide(**20**). Yield: 80%. Pale yellow solid. mp: 254 °C. ¹H NMR; 11.645(1-NH, br-s), 11.257(1-NH-N, br-s), 8.68 (CH=N, s) 8.274(1-H, s, aromatic), 8.144 and 7.92 (2H, -NH₂-brs), 8.102(1-H, s, aromatic), 7.522(m, 2-H, aromatic), 2.77(3-H, s), 2.56(3-H, s). ¹³C NMR: 177.65, 142.37, 140.92, 139.13, 131.37, 127.84, 125.63, 125.20, 124.95, 123.48, 120.27, 119.01, 113.60, 111.67, 17.06, 15.46. HRMS (ESI-Q-TOF): C₁₆H₁₅BrN₄S [M+H]⁺ calcd *m/z*, 374.0200, found *m/z*(M+1) 375.0252.
- (E)-2-((6-methoxy-1,4-dimethyl-9-*H*-carbazol-3-yl)methylene)hydrazine carbothioamide (**21**) Yield: 70%. Pale yellow solid; mp: 244° C. IR (KBr): 3422.63, 3348, 3287.32, 2825, 1588.13, 1537.96, 1495, 1316, 1208, 1040 cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR: 11.35(1- Indole N-H br-s), 11.25(1-NH-N, br s), 8.68(1H, CH=N, s), 8.12 and 7.85 (2H-NH₂-C=S, 2 br-s), 8.00(1-H, s aromatic), 7.7(1-H, s, aromatic), 7.45(d, 1H, aromatic), 7.05(d, 1-H, V), 3.85(3H, OCH₃), 2.82(3-H, s), 2.49(3-H, s). HRMS (ESI-Q-TOF): C₁₇H₁₈N₄OS [M + H]⁺ calcd *m/z* 326.1201, found *m/z* (M+1) 327.1294
- (E)-2-((6-hydroxy-1,4-dimethyl-9-*H*-carbazol-3-yl)methylene)hydrazine carbothioamide (**22**). Yield: 80%. Off White solid. ¹H NMR; 11.659(1indole-NH, brs), 11.286(1-NH-N, brs), 8.48(CH=N, s), 8.406(1-H, s, aromatic), 8.144 and 7.92 (2H, -NH₂-brs), 8.28(d, 1-H), 8.070(1-H, d), 7.531(2-H, d), 3.10(3-H, N-CH₃, s), 2.77(3-H, s), 2.56(3-H, s). ¹³C NMR: 177.65, 141.95, 140.92, 139.15, 131.31, 127.88, 125.62, 124.98, 123.32, 120.32, 118.96, 113.61, 111.67, 31.0, 17.14, 15.46. HRMS(ESI-Q-TOF): C₁₆H₁₆N₄OS [M+H]⁺ calcd *m/z*, 312.1044, found *m/z*(M+1) 313.1129
- (E)-2-((1,4-dimethyl-9-*H*-carbazol-3-yl)methylene)N-methylhydrazinecarbothio amide (**23**). Yield: 70%. Light blue solid. HNMR: 11.35(1- Indole N-H br s), 11.25(1-NH-N, br s), 8.68(CH=N, s), 8.12 and 7.89 (-NH₂, 2 br-s) 8.00(1-H, s aromatic), 7.7(1-H, s aromatic), 7.45(d, 1H), 7.05(d, 1-H), 3.85(3-H, OCH₃), 2.82(3-H, s), 2.49(3-H, s), ¹³C NMR: 177.30, 177.1221, 141.8346, 139.9849, 124.95, 123.80, 123.39, 122.64, 122.44, 120.71, 119.41, 118.16, 111.25, 30.85, 16.75, 15.70 HRMS(ESI-Q-TOF) C₁₇H₁₈N₄S calcd *m/z* 310.1252 found *m/z*(M+1) 311.1324
- (E)-2-((6-fluoro-1,4-dimethyl-9-*H*-carbazol-3-yl)N-methylene)N-methyl hydrazine carbothioamide (**24**). Yield: 80%, off white solid. ¹H NMR: 11.49(1-Indole N-H br s), 11.24(1-NH-N, br s), 8.66 (CH=N, s), 8.36 (1H, aromatic),

8.01(NH=CS, s, aromatic), 7.91(1-H,d aromatic),7.51(dd,2H,aromatic),7.25(1-H,t,aromatic),3.33(3H,N-CH₃), 2.78(3-H,s,CH₃),2.49(3-H,s,CH₃).HRMS (ESI-Q-TOF):.C₁₇H₁₇FN₄S [M+H]⁺ calcd *m/z* ,328.1158, found *m/z* 329.1034

- (E)-2-((6-bromo-1,4-dimethyl-9-*H*-carbazol-3-yl)methylene)N-methyl hydrazine carbothioamide (**26**). Yield: 80%, off white solid. ¹HNMR: 11.65(1-Indole N-H br s), 11.28(1-NH-N, br s), 8.67 (CH=N,s), 8.40 (1H,aromatic), 8.03(NH=CS,s, aromatic), 8.25(1-H,d aromatic),7.51(dd,2H,aromatic), 3.33(3H,N-CH₃),2.78(3-H,s,CH₃),2.49(3-H,s,CH₃).HRMS (ESI-Q-TOF):.C₁₇H₁₇FN₄S [M+H]⁺ calcd *m/z* ,388.0357, found *m/z* 389.0410
- (E)-2-((6-methoxy-1,4-dimethyl-9-*H*-carbazol-3-yl)methylene)N-methyl-hydrazine carbothioamide (**27**). Yield: 80%, light yellow solid.¹HNMR(dmso-d₆): 11.30(1-Indole N-H br-s), 11.22(1-NH-N, br s), 8.63(1H,CH=N,s), 8.05(NH-C=S, br-s) 8.00(1-H,s aromatic),7.6(1-H,s, aromatic), 7.45(d,1H, aromatic), 7.05(d,1-H,aromatic),3.86(3H,OCH₃), 3.05(3-H,N-CH₃,s), 2.80(3-H,s), 2.49(3-H,s). HRMS (ESI-Q-TOF): C₁₆H₁₆N₄S [M + H]⁺ calcd *m/z* , 296.11found *m/z* 297.1165
- (E)-2-((6-hydroxy-1,4-dimethyl-9-*H*-carbazol-3-yl)methylene)N-methylhydrazine carbothioamide (**28**). Yield: 75%. Off white solid.¹HNMR(dmso-d₆):11.24(1-Indole-N-H, br, s), 11.13(1-NH-N,brs), 8.97(1-OH,s),7.96(NH-C=S),8.63(CH=N,s),8.35(1H,d,aromtic),7.96(1-H,s,NH-CH₃),7.55(1-H,aromatic,d),7.34(1-H,aromatic,d),6.91(1-H,aromatic,dd),3.05(3-H,N-CH₃,s),2.78(3-H,CH₃),2.51(3-H,CH₃).HRMS(ESI-Q-TOF):.C₁₇H₁₈N₄OS [M + H]⁺ calcd *m/z* 326.1201 found *m/z*(M+1) 327.1240

2.3 Analysis of synthesized compounds

All the compounds were well confirmed by NMR, and HRMS. ¹H and ¹³CNMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance II and JEOL 400 MHz NMR instrument. Molecular mass of the compounds was determined by HRMS MASS spectroscopy using a Micromass, Q-ToF micro (Water make) spectrophotometer.

Figure 4 Proton NMR spectra of compound (E)-2-((1,4-dimethyl-9-H-carbazol-yl)methylene)hydrazinecarbothioamide (17) in Deuterated DMSO solvent (above) and DMSO-D₆ + D₂O solvent (below)

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Chemistry

Synthesis of 6th position substituted carbazole (R=H,F,Cl,Br, OCH₃,OH) bearing with or without substituted thiosemicarbazide (R₁=H,CH₃) 17-28 done from starting material 6-substituted 1,4-dimethyl-9-H-carbazol-3-carbaldehyde (R=H,F,Cl, Br, OCH₃,OH) (11-16) intermediate reported in our previous reserach paper method [9]. All final compounds (17-28) were well analyzed by proton NMR experiment (Figure 4) where appearance of six aromatic proton of 1,4-dimethyl-9-H-carbazole structure around 7-8.5 ppm. Three separate broad singlet peaks around δ = 11.5, 11.25 and 8.20-7.90 ppm respectively were assigned to indole 9-NH of carbazole scaffold, N-NH groups, NH₂-C=S, proton respectively. The two characteristic methyl peaks in 1,4-dimethyl-9-H-carbazole found around δ value 2.50 and 2.71 ppm respectively in proton NMR spectra. In the ¹H NMR spectra of compounds 17-28, the signal due to the CH=N proton was observed in the NMR spectra at 8.5– 8.6 ppm gives Schiff base formation i.e., linking of carbazole scaffold to thiosemicarbazide part formation. All exchangeable proton likes indole 9-NH, N-NH and NH₂-C=S groups were also disappeared on addition of deuterated solvent D₂O in DMSO-d₆ proton NMR spectra further proven existence of these final compounds (Figure 4). In the HRMS spectroscopy of some few compounds, the M+1 peak was observed for the compounds (17= 297.1165, 18 = 315.1256., 19 = 331.0806, 20 = 375.0252, 21 = 327.1294, 22 = 313.1129, 23 = 311.1324, 24 = 329.1034, 26 = 389.0410, 27 = 297.1165, 28 = 327.1240 further confirmed the formation of 17-28.

3.2 *In vitro* anticancer study

MTT assay was carried to determine their *in vitro* anticancer activity (IC₅₀) of all synthesized compounds (17-28) on the U87 human glioma cell line for 24 h time period. Results of *in vitro* anticancer profile were analysed on the basis of IC₅₀ values were compared to standard drug TMZ shown in **Table -1** [9, 29]. The IC₅₀ values of Mahanine, a pyranocarbazole alkaloid showed potential *in vitro* anticancer activity (IC₅₀) in a range of 12- 15 μ M against glioma cell lines viz. LN229 and U87MG cells respectively after 48 h using MTT assay by Bhattacharya K et al. [30, 31]. All final compounds (17-28) divided in two series (A, B) showed IC₅₀ values in the range of 21 μ M-215 μ M (Table 2). In series A, IC₅₀ values of 6-substituted-1,4-dimethyl-9-H-thiosemicarbazide derivative (R= F, Br, Cl, OCH₃, OH and R₁ = H) 17-22 were found to be 26.50 μ M (17), 160 μ M (18), 140 μ M (19), 34.00 μ M (20), 39.00 μ M (21), 80.00 μ M (22) respectively. *In vitro* anticancer activity profile was found in the order of 17 (H) >20 (OCH₃) >21 (Br) > 22 (OH) >19 (Cl) > 18 (F). In series A, four compounds 17, 20, 21, 22 showed better anticancer activities on the human glioma U87 MG cell line than temozolomide (100 μ M) [9, 29, 32]. Electronegative elements like fluoro, chloro substitution imparts inductive and mesomeric effect, whereas bromo substitution exhibits mostly mesomeric effect found play an important role for potent *in vitro* anticancer activity in series A [9, 33]. In series B, IC₅₀ values of 6-substituted-1,4-dimethyl-N-methyl-thiosemicarbazide derivative (R= F, Br, Cl, OCH₃, OH and R₁ = CH₃) 23-28 were found to be 62 μ M (23), 215 μ M (24), 198 μ M (25), 161 μ M (26), 183.32 μ M (27), 50.00 μ M (28) respectively, and their activity profile was in the order of 23 (H) >28(OH)>26 (OCH₃) >27 (Br) > 25 (Cl) > 24 (F). Methyl substitution on thiosemicarbazide part or varying substitution on 6th position on carbazole core based thiosemicarbazide derivatives (23-28) showed loss of anticancer activities on the U87MG cell line were

observed (**Figure 5**). Based on the *in vitro* anticancer data of all compounds (**17-28**) showed that series A, were found better than series B on the U87MG cell line

Table 1 *In vitro* cytotoxicity (IC₅₀) profile for the compounds (17-28)

S.NO.	R	R ₁	IC ₅₀ (μM)
17	H	H	26.50 ±6.24
18	F	H	160 ±12.24
19	Cl	H	140 ±12.24
20	Br	H	34.00 ±12.24
21	OCH ₃	H	39.00 ±12.24
22	OH	H	80.00 ±12.24
23	H	CH ₃	62.00 ±12.24
24	F	CH ₃	215 ±12.24
25	Cl	CH ₃	198 ±12.24
26	Br	CH ₃	161.00 ±12.24
27	OCH ₃	CH ₃	183.32 ±12.24
28	OH	CH ₃	50.00
Temozolomide	-----	-----	100
Carmustine	-----	-----	18.24

Figure 5 SAR analysis based on *in vitro* anticancer activity of final compounds against U87 MG human glioma cell line

4 Conclusion

In this research work, we synthesized substituted carbazole bearing thiosemicarbazides Schiff based derivatives (17-28) incorporating different electron-donating and withdrawing groups was prepared and their structure were well characterized by different analytical spectroscopy techniques. SAR study was also well established based on *in vitro* cytotoxicity (IC₅₀) data of all final compounds (17-28) evaluated against human glioma U87 MG cell line using MTT assay. SAR studies of all carbazoles bearing thiosemicarbazide derivatives showed that no substituent on 6th position of carbazole scaffold (R =H) or bromo or methoxy group and also no substituent on thiosemicarbazide moiety (R₁ =H) necessary for potent anticancer activity on the U87MG cell line. Mesomeric or inductive effect due to electron donating or electron withdrawing group on 6th position of carbazole group bearing with thiosemicarbazide moiety also found crucial role for anticancer activities. *In vitro* anticancer studies of carbazole bearing thiosemicarbazide derivatives (17-28) can be helpful to further in vivo of these potential novel anticancer agents against brain tumors.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

Professor Pratibha Metha Luthra is very grateful to Department of Science and Technology (DST), India (SR/SO/HS-40/2004) for project. Dr. Nitin Kumar (9/45(1337)2014-EMR-1) is thankful to CSIR, New Delhi, India, for giving financial support (SRF). We are very grateful to University Instrumentation Facility (USIC), University of Delhi, India, for providing NMR, HRMS provided through the central instrumental facilities:

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declared that article content has no conflicts of interest.

References

- [1] Louis DN, Ohgaki H, Wiestler OD, Cavenee WK, Burger PC, Jouvet A, Scheithauer BW, Kleihues P. The 2007 WHO classification of tumours of the central nervous system. *Acta neuropathologica*. 2007 Aug, 114(2):97-109.
- [2] Hanif F, Muzaffar K, Perveen K, Malhi SM, Simjee SU. Glioblastoma multiforme: a review of its epidemiology and pathogenesis through clinical presentation and treatment. *Asian Pacific journal of cancer prevention: APJCP*. 2017, 18(1):3.
- [3] Jain A, Lai JC, Chowdhury GM, Behar K, Bhushan A. Glioblastoma: current chemotherapeutic status and need for new targets and approaches. *Brain tumors: current and emerging therapeutic strategies*. Rijeka: InTech. 2011 Aug 23:145-76.
- [4] Vehlow A, Cordes N (2013) Invasion as target for therapy of glioblastoma multiforme. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-Reviews on Cancer* 1836: 236-244.
- [5] Luthra PM, Lal N. Prospective of curcumin, a pleiotropic signalling molecule from *Curcuma longa* in the treatment of Glioblastoma. *European journal of medicinal chemistry*. 2016 Feb 15, 109:23-35.
- [6] Mongre RK, Mishra CB, Prakash A, Jung S, Lee BS, Kumari S, Hong JT, Lee MS. Novel carbazole-piperazine hybrid small molecule induces apoptosis by targeting BCL-2 and inhibits tumor progression in lung adenocarcinoma *in vitro* and xenograft mice model. *Cancers*. 2019 Aug 25, 11(9):1245.
- [7] Luthra PM, Kumar N. Progress and Development of C-3, C-6, and N-9 Positions Substituted Carbazole Integrated Molecular Hybrid Molecules as Potential Anticancer Agents. *Mini Reviews in Medicinal Chemistry*. 2021 Nov 1, 21(19):2929-56.
- [8] Kumar N, Gupta P, Bansal S. Progress and Development of Carbazole Scaffold Based as Potential Anti-Alzheimer Agents Using MTDL Approach. *Letters in Drug Design & Discovery*. 2022 Dec 1, 19(12):1049-67.
- [9] Kumar N, Lal N, Nemaish V, Luthra PM. Design, synthesis, DNA binding studies and evaluation of anticancer potential of novel substituted bis-carbazole derivatives against human glioma U87 MG cell line. *Bioorganic Chemistry*. 2020 Jul 1, 100:103911.
- [10] Głuszyńska A. Biological potential of carbazole derivatives. *European journal of medicinal chemistry*. 2015 Apr 13, 94:405-26.
- [11] Dumat B, Bordeau G, Faurel-Paul E, Mahuteau-Betzer F, Saettel N, Bomble M, Metgé G, Charra F, Fiorini-Debuisschert C, Teulade-Fichou MP. N-phenyl-carbazole-based two-photon fluorescent probes: strong sequence dependence of the duplex vs quadruplex selectivity. *Biochimie*. 2011 Aug 1, 93(8):1209-18.
- [12] Caruso A, Sinicropi MS, Lancelot JC, El-Kashef H, Saturnino C, Aubert G, Ballandonne C, Lesnard A, Cresteil T, Dallemagne P, Rault S. Synthesis and evaluation of cytotoxic activities of new guanidines derived from carbazoles. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters*. 2014 Jan 15, 24(2):467-72.
- [13] Çiftçi GA, Temel HE, Yıldırım ŞU, Kaplancıklı ZA, Altıntop MD, Genç L. Apoptotic effects of some carbazole derivatives on lung carcinoma and glioma cell lines. *Medicinal Chemistry Research*. 2013 Aug, 22(8):3751-9.
- [14] Chen C-M, Syu J-P, Way T-D, Huang L-J, Kuo S-C, et al. (2015) BC3EE2, 9B, a synthetic carbazole derivative, upregulates autophagy and synergistically sensitizes human GBM8901 glioblastoma cells to temozolomide. *International journal of molecular medicine* 36: 1244-1252.

- [15] Diaz P, Horne E, Xu C, Hamel E, Wagenbach M, Petrov RR, Uhlenbruck B, Haas B, Hothi P, Wordeman L, Gussio R. Modified carbazoles destabilize microtubules and kill glioblastoma multiform cells. *European journal of medicinal chemistry*. 2018 Nov 5;159:74-89.
- [16] Heffeter P, Pape VF, Enyedy ÉA, Keppler BK, Szakacs G, Kowol CR. Anticancer thiosemicarbazones: chemical properties, interaction with iron metabolism, and resistance development. *Antioxidants & redox signaling*. 2019 Mar 1, 30(8):1062-82.
- [17] Acharya PT, Bhavsar ZA, Jethava DJ, Patel DB, Patel HD. A review on development of bio-active thiosemicarbazide derivatives: Recent advances. *Journal of Molecular Structure*. 2021 Feb 15, 1226:129268.
- [18] Li HQ, Lv PC, Yan T, Zhu HL. Urea derivatives as anticancer agents. *Anti-Cancer Agents in Medicinal Chemistry (Formerly Current Medicinal Chemistry-Anti-Cancer Agents)*. 2009 May 1, 9(4):471-80.
- [19] Pelosi G. Thiosemicarbazone metal complexes: from structure to activity. *The Open Crystallography Journal*. 2010 Mar 25, 3(1).
- [20] French FA, Blanz Jr EJ. The carcinostatic activity of α -(N) heterocyclic carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazones: I. Isoquinoline-1-carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone. *Cancer research*. 1965 Oct, 25(9_Part_1):1454-8.
- [21] Guo ZL, Richardson DR, Kalinowski DS, Kovacevic Z, Tan-Un KC, Chan GC. The novel thiosemicarbazone, di-2-pyridylketone-4-cyclohexyl-4-methyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (DpC), inhibits neuroblastoma growth *in vitro* and *in vivo* via multiple mechanisms. *Journal of hematology & oncology*. 2016 Dec, 9(1):1-6.
- [22] Quach P, Gutierrez E, Basha MT, Kalinowski DS, Sharpe PC, Lovejoy DB, Bernhardt PV, Jansson PJ, Richardson DR. Methemoglobin formation by triapine, di-2-pyridylketone-4, 4-dimethyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (Dp44mT), and other anticancer thiosemicarbazones: identification of novel thiosemicarbazones and therapeutics that prevent this effect. *Molecular pharmacology*. 2012 Jul 1, 82(1):105-14.
- [23] Kajal A, Bala S, Kamboj S, Sharma N, Saini V. Schiff bases: a versatile pharmacophore. *Journal of Catalysts*. 2013 Aug 27, 2013.
- [24] Parekh NM, Mistry BM, Pandurangan M, Shinde SK, Patel RV. Investigation of anticancer potencies of newly generated Schiff base imidazolylphenylheterocyclic-2-ylmethylenethiazole-2-amines. *Chinese Chemical Letters*. 2017 Mar 1, 28(3):602-6.
- [25] Mosmann T. Rapid colorimetric assay for cellular growth and survival: application to proliferation and cytotoxicity assays. *Journal of immunological methods*. 1983 Dec 16, 65(1-2):55-63.
- [26] Guthrie RW, Brossi A, Mennona FA, Mullin JG, Kierstead RW, Grunberg E. Ellipticine derivatives. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. 1975 Jul, 18(7):755-60.
- [27] Dalton LK, Demerac S, Teitei T. Synthesis of pyridocarbazoles for anti-tumour studies. *Australian Journal of Chemistry*. 1969, 22(1):185-95.
- [28] Metwally MA, Bondock S, El-Azap H, Kandeel EE. Thiosemicarbazides: synthesis and reactions. *Journal of Sulfur Chemistry*. 2011 Oct 1, 32(5):489-519.
- [29] Kidwai M, Jain A, Nemaish V, Kumar R, Luthra PM. Efficient entry to diversely functionalized spirooxindoles from isatin and their biological activity. *Medicinal Chemistry Research*. 2013 Jun, 22(6):2717-23.
- [30] Bhattacharya K, Bag AK, Tripathi R, Samanta SK, Pal BC, Shaha C, Mandal C. Mahanine, a novel mitochondrial complex-III inhibitor induces G0/G1 arrest through redox alteration-mediated DNA damage response and regresses glioblastoma multiforme. *American journal of cancer research*. 2014, 4(6):629.
- [31] Nitin Kumar, Krishna Kumar Singh and Pratibha Mehta Luthra (2021), A REVIEW ON ANTICANCER POTENTIAL OF SOME PYRANOCARBAZOLE ALKALOIDS AND ITS DERIVATIVES *Int. J. of Adv. Res.* 9 [Jun]. 874-883 [ISSN 2320-5407]. www.journalijar.com
- [32] Kumar N, Kumar R, Nemaish V, Lal N, Luthra PM. Bis ((1, 4-dimethyl-9 H-carbazol-3-yl) methyl) amine-mediated anticancer effect triggered by sequence-specific cleavage of DNA leading to programmed cell death in the human U87 cell line. *RSC advances*. 2016;6(72):67925-40.
- [33] Mishra CB, Sharma D, Prakash A, Kumari N, Kumar N, Luthra PM. Design and synthesis of (4E)-4-(4-substitutedbenzylideneamino)-3-substituted-2,3-dihydro-2-thioxothiazole-5-carbonitrile as novel A2A receptor antagonists. *Bioorganic & medicinal chemistry*. 2013 Oct 1, 21(19):6077-83.